

Session 42

Theatre 11

Guideline to validate sensor output of animal-based measurements

J. Maselyne¹, A. Stygar², M. Pastell², Q. Allueva Molina³, A. Ramon Pérez³, P. Llonch³, H. L. Ko³

¹ ILVO, Burg Van Gansberghelaan 115b1, 9820 Merelbeke, Belgium, ² Luke, Latokartanonkaari 9, 00790 Helsinki, Finland, ³ Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Plaça Cívica, 08193 Barcelona, Spain

Sensor technology is used in precision livestock farming applications to monitor amongst others animal health and welfare. However, in order to effectively use sensor data for welfare monitoring, the sensors need to provide valid and reliable measurements and the measured data needs to be relevant for animal welfare. Thus, sensor validation is crucial for applications in commercial and research settings. For this validation process, there is a need for a standardized procedure, so that the performance of validation trials are comparable and can lead to a reliable outcome. In the context of the aWISH (HEurope, 101060818) and Clearfarm (H2020, 862919) projects, a guideline is set up to develop a standardized protocol for sensor validation, divided into steps organized into two main blocks. Block 1 is dedicated to output validation, meaning whether the sensor is measuring the output it is designed to measure accurately. Block 2 is dedicated to welfare relevance validation, meaning whether sensor output can provide information regarding animal welfare and can be used as an animal welfare indicator. This presentation will focus mainly on Block 1, which includes different steps: (1) description of the sensor output, (2) determination of the gold standard and reference output, (3) determination of sample size and statistical analysis, (4) limitations of the technology. The guidelines will be illustrated using a number of case studies in cattle, pigs and poultry covering cameras, microphones, wearables, load cells and a combination of sensors.

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AgrifoodTEF's pioneering EU service provider from research to industry for the development of Artificial Intelligence and robotic solutions

Z. Guy¹, J. M. Gautier¹, J. Contreras²

¹ Institut de l'Élevage, 149 Rue de Bercy, 75595 Paris, France, ² Acta, 149 Rue de Bercy, 75595 Paris, France

The AgrifoodTEF project positions itself at the forefront of innovative synergies in the agricultural sector by promoting the development and validation of cutting-edge solutions based on artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics. By bridging the gap between researchers and private companies, this project marks a significant evolution in applied research, where research institutions offer customized services to industrials to support the development of advanced technologies. A tangible example of this collaboration is seen at Derval experimental farm, where video monitoring solutions for cattle are being assessed. Preliminary discussions between researchers and Ag-Tech companies help to precisely define technical and technological requirements such as the optimal placement of cameras, image quality requirements, and necessary data storage capacities. The design of services offered to companies is then modular, allowing customization according to the specific needs of each company. The services range from providing raw video recordings to external validation of the developed solution with the possibility for the company to add services such as provision of complementary data, video annotation, co-construction of test protocols and more. This modular approach ensures companies to build a service tailored to their objectives. This collaboration between research and industry results in a win-win relationship. For the research sector, it enhances the added-value of experimental facilities and asserts its expertise and experimental know-how. For companies, it offers the opportunity to advance in the development of their solutions and to test them under real conditions through the expertise of recognized researchers. AgrifoodTEF leverages the access to the European network of Testing and Experimental Facilities. AgrifoodTEF emerges as a European network offering a range of services to Ag-Tech companies, highlighting synergies and the diversity of production situations, thereby enriching the agricultural sector with innovative solutions that are tested to be market-ready.